

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONSUMER SERVICES MARKET

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Abstract: This article examines the issue of modern trends in the placement of consumer services enterprises in modern conditions. The analysis shows changes in the principles of development of a network of consumer services enterprises in the areas of new buildings, as well as the need to improve approaches to planning the retail and consumer infrastructure of residential areas. Based on the survey results, the author studied the factors influencing the behavior of consumers of individual services.

Key words: personal services, placement of enterprises, questionnaire survey, planning of personal services enterprises.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada zamonaviy sharoitlarda maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarini joylashtirishning zamonaviy tendentsiyalari masalasi ko'rib chiqiladi. Tahlil yangi binolar hududlarida maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalari tarmog'ini rivojlantirish tamoyillari o'zgarganligini, shuningdek, turar-joy massivlarining chakana savdo va maishiy infratuzilmasini rejalashtirishga yondashuvlarni takomillashtirish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. So'rov natijalariga ko'ra, muallif alohida xizmatlar iste'molchilarining xatti-harakatlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni o'rganib chiqdi.

Kalit so'zlar: shaxsiy xizmatlar, korxonalarining joylashuvi, anketa so'rovi, shaxsiy xizmatlar korxonalarini rejalashtirish.

Аннотация: В данной статье изучается вопрос современных тенденций размещения предприятий бытового сервиса в современных условиях. Анализ показывает изменения в принципах развития сети предприятий бытовых услуг в районах новостроек, а также необходимость совершенствования подходов к планированию торгово-бытовой инфраструктуры жилых массивов. На основании результатов опроса, автором изучены факторы, влияющие на поведение потребителей индивидуальных услуг.

Ключевые слова: бытовые услуги, размещение предприятий, анкетный опрос, планирование предприятий бытовых услуг.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, Uzbekistan is undergoing a large-scale reform in the field of housing construction. First of all, this affects the appearance of cities. In recent years, there has been a transition from low-rise construction to the construction of high-rise buildings and high-rise construction. The creation in every major city of a so-called "city" with houses of 12-16 floors and above leads to changes in the communal, transport and social infrastructure. In addition, in rural settlements there is also a transition to the construction of multi-storey apartment buildings.

The result of changes in urban planning policy are serious changes in trade and consumer services for the population. High population density and increased living comfort have led to stricter requirements for the organization of consumer services. More and more new types of consumer preferences regarding individual services are being formed. For example, delivery of goods and services directly to your home is becoming the norm. Digital technologies for providing individual services are increasingly developing.

In these conditions, improving the methodology for locating retail trade and consumer service enterprises becomes an important problem. Modern trends in the development of the service sector in populated areas indicate the need to abandon the traditional regulatory method of locating consumer service enterprises. Firstly, the previous classification of individual and household services has long been outdated due to fundamental changes in the living conditions of the population. Secondly, the need for individual services varies sharply not only across districts, but also within one small district.

Until now, the main indicator of the development of the service sector, in particular consumer service enterprises, is the provision of the population with the number of places or other indicators of capacity (the number of

places in hairdressing salons, the number of visits to consumer service enterprises, the number of workshops per 1000 residents, etc.). The development experience of countries shows that the high quality of the service sector does not directly depend on the standard density of the network of service enterprises.

ANALYSIS OF THE LITERATURE USED

The development of the consumer service system and its effectiveness have been the subject of research by many scientists. Goncharov A.A. in his research he proposes the concept of a system for managing the development and support of consumer services for the population. This system, through local governments, should ensure the effectiveness of the development of a network of consumer service enterprises. Shadskaya I.G., exploring trends in the development of the market for household services in rural areas, identifies such market segments as dynamically developing, having development potential, and being in a stage of decline. The author proposes to organize marketing research on the part of municipal authorities, as well as to develop a program for the development of the consumer services market at the regional level, including, in particular, regulatory and information support for this market. In the work of Mairova A.Yu. Based on a detailed analysis of the structure of the consumer services market, it is proposed to improve the management system through the creation of municipal departments of consumer services. Some authors focus on the development of management of enterprises in the sphere of consumer services in the framework of optimizing their number and density. There are also developments based on the development of the consumer services market as a mechanism for regulating the supply of individual services. Analysis of the research carried out allowed us to conclude that in the development of the consumer services market it is necessary to plan the placement of a network of enterprises in this area.

It is necessary to pay tribute to scientists who have made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing in economics, and research conducted in the field of economics in our country for many years was based on national characteristics. These include M. Muhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov, Abdullaev Yu., Saliev A., Sharifkhodzhaev M., Khodiev B., Rakhimova D., Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh., Sh. Musaeva and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research process, a systematic approach, abstract logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and sampling observation methods were used.

Based on this concept, the formation of a network of consumer service enterprises in the regions is carried out according to the principle of sufficiency, that is, there should be as many enterprises as needed for a certain amount of the population. This approach is accepted not only by local government bodies, but also by entrepreneurs themselves. Local authorities use this approach when allocating land for the creation of business structures. For example, if there is already a shoe repair shop in the area, a new one is considered inappropriate. At the same time, entrepreneurs themselves, purely psychologically, do not want to enter into competition with an existing enterprise.

This approach leads to the fact that consumer service providers have virtually no competitors in the local market. The most important thing is that with this approach there is an outflow of customers from this local market.

At the same time, the experience of developing beauty salons (bridal service salons) in the cities and villages of Uzbekistan shows that tougher competition and the concentration of several enterprises in a small geographical area contributes to the influx of clients and maintaining the income of all entrepreneurs. We observe exactly the same effect for other types of consumer service enterprises, as well as for retail trade enterprises. The location of several identical retail outlets nearby does not lead to a decrease in the number of customers, but, on the contrary, to their increase. This trend is also observed in the development of a network of pharmacies, diagnostic centers, "chicken houses", real estate agencies, etc. We believe that this situation is due to changes in consumer behavior of the population.

The problem of researching the market for household services in the Republic of Uzbekistan is associated with the lack of a system of statistical monitoring of its condition. Public service enterprises appear in two sections of statistical reporting: services and the state of small business and entrepreneurship. However, analysis of statistical reporting shows that household services are not directly reflected in them. In the services reporting section, personal services appear in individual services, other services, and retail trade services. In the reporting section for small businesses, there is also no clear picture for consumer service enterprises. Moreover, in analytical studies of recent years, the market for household services has been practically not studied. Based on this, in our research we focused on studying the state of individual services.

Observations show that a high concentration of individual and small enterprises is typical for the sphere of individual services to the population, that is, all of the above business entities are in one way or another connected with direct contact with the client. As the main concept for studying this problem, we used one effective method of marketing research - the questionnaire survey method. This method attracts attention due to its simplicity, low time consumption and coverage of different categories of consumers.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A questionnaire survey was conducted among potential consumers of individual services. Our research in several districts of the city of Samarkand and rural settlements showed the following features of consumer preferences in the provision of individual services. The research concerned the study of factors influencing the choice of a particular retail and consumer services enterprise. The respondents were residents of the area who agreed to answer several questions in the survey. The questionnaire consisted of the following questions:

- Enjoy the convenient location of retail and consumer services businesses in the area.
- What is the route for visiting retail and consumer services businesses?
- What has the greatest influence on the choice of specific retail and consumer services businesses?
- Which location of consumer services enterprises do you consider most attractive?

As an initial premise, we accepted this study as exploratory, so the respondents' answers were also considered preliminary. In addition, the conditions of the survey and anonymity do not allow the results of this survey to be used as the basis for serious scientific conclusions.

At the same time, we consider the respondents' answers worthy of attention. The overwhelming majority of respondents answered the first question positively, that is, they are satisfied with the state of the trade and household infrastructure of their place of residence.

To the second question, about 50% of respondents indicated visiting several enterprises at once, over 35% indicated a traditional visit to selected retail outlets on the way home, and only 12% had a specific object visited.

The third question of the questionnaire allowed respondents to express their own opinions, so it was not possible to choose one priority factor. The most common answers include: loyalty to one seller, attractive prices, assortment offered, choice, honesty of the seller, good service.

The respondents were interested in the question of the structure of consumer service enterprises, that is, the uneven density of their location. The answers to the fourth question were arranged in the following sequence: close to the place of residence - 44%, possibility of parking a car - 38%, on the way to work - 12%, no definite choice - 6%. It should be noted that respondents have a positive attitude towards the presence of several similar service enterprises at once.

Based on the research we conducted, we systematized the main motives for evaluating household infrastructure enterprises from consumers. These include: the presence of freedom to choose the subject of the provision of household services, that is, there should be as many of these enterprises as possible; ensuring the accessibility of household services, that is, their location and operating hours should be unlimited; variety of services offered, that is, taking into account individual needs in the offer and provision of individual services; quality of service provision, that is, completeness and speed of service.

The conducted research allowed us to formulate a concept for the development of the consumer services market, the main provision of which is the creation of conditions for the free formation of supply in the consumer services market. In the implementation of the proposed concept, special attention is paid to the lack of regulation of the number of consumer service enterprises, as well as to stimulating their growth through self-employment programs for the population.

CONCLUSION

Based on the theoretical and practical research conducted, we propose the development of new approaches to the development of the household services market, based on stimulating competition in this area. It is necessary to create an environment for consumer services, which includes an unlimited number of subjects providing household services. In addition, it is proposed to move from the distributed nature of the location of enterprises to the nodal principle, that is, the concentration of several similar household services enterprises in a limited area, which will stimulate the consumption of these services.

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